

Job satisfaction among primary health care nurses

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to analyze the job satisfaction of nurses in primary health care facilities. This study employed a quantitative descriptive design. The research used a cross-sectional approach. This study involved 226 nurses who worked in 15 inpatients primary health care. The sampling technique uses a proportionate simple random sampling technique. Nurse job satisfaction instruments assessed context factors and content factors. Nurse job satisfaction on context factor was in a good category by a big responsibility for nurse's work (55.2%), progress in work developed well (63.4%), nurses had the opportunity to achieve achievement (54.5%), nurses got great recognition for performance (58.6%) and felt their work is valuable (65.5%). Job satisfaction was supported by policy indicators, supervision, salary, interpersonal relationships, and good working conditions. On the other hand, nurses' job satisfaction on the content factor still needs to be optimized. This is supported by the job satisfaction of nurses on the indicators of responsibility, achievement, performance recognition that has not reached 60%. Therefore, job satisfaction among nurses in inpatient primary health care was quite good enough but still requires optimization on the content factor.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Society is starting to realize the importance of health, professionalism, and high quality from health service to reach high service quality requires a strong and quality resource component, including human resources [1], [2]. Primary health care is the foremost and closest health service place to the community which has a public service function and a medical service function. Primary health care services are comprehensive providers, covering aspects of promotion, prevention of health problems, treatment, and recovery [3], [4].

Nurses are an important component in a health service at primary health care. The number of nurses dominates until (55-65%). Nursing services are carried out constantly and continuously for 24 hours to patients every day [3], [5]. This reality shows the large contribution of the nursing profession in determining the quality of health services. Based on several studies on the average productive working time of nurses at primary health care in Indonesia about 46.8% was used for non-productive and 53.2% for productive activities. On the other hand, about 39.9% is used for visitor activities [6], [7]. This shows a problem related to the performance of nurses in providing health services because of lack of patient satisfaction at the primary health care caused by waiting time for emergency care, nurse vacancies, responsiveness, competence, and visit schedules [8]–[10]. Nurses who experience low work motivation can reduce the quality of nursing care delivery [11]–[13]. Nurses

still think that their high workload is not supported by appropriate policies will further reduce work motivation [12], [14], [15]. The situation was exacerbated by the violations committed by the troubled nurse.

The results of the preliminary study indicate that the nursing service gap can be caused by the unsatisfactory working of the nursing services. Nurse job satisfaction is very important in an effort to maximize the quality of health services because satisfaction is one component of work motivation. Staff job satisfaction is the result or response of individual perceptions of factors in their work and is supported by social factors [16]. According to Herzberg's theory, job satisfaction is also influenced by intrinsic factors (achievement, recognition, responsibility, and progress) and extrinsic factors (salary, security, working conditions, employment status, standards, supervision, and interpersonal relationships) [17]. Job satisfaction status can affect the implementation of the next job. Self-actualization of workers can be formed from the job satisfaction they have. A nurse's psychological maturity is determined by job satisfaction. Failure to achieve job satisfaction can result in decreased morale, work fatigue and unstable emotional conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to do research that can provide an overview of the job satisfaction of nurses in basic services.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This was a descriptive quantitative study with a cross-sectional approach. This study examined the job satisfaction among nurses at primary health care. The respondents of this study are 226 nurses who served in 15 primary health care inpatients in Demak Regency, Central Java, Indonesia. The inclusion criteria were nurses with undergraduate education, registered as nursing staff at inpatient health centres in Demak Regency and willing to become participants. Meanwhile, the exclusion criteria were nurses with chronic illness and still in study assignment at a university. Chronic illness will disrupt a person's psychology and have an impact on satisfaction. Moreover, staff who are pursuing high-level education are sometimes more satisfied with their jobs because of their learning and career opportunities. These exclusion criteria are confounding factors and need to manage in this study. The sampling technique was carried out using a proportionate simple random sampling. This study had been declared ethically qualified according to the ethical clearance certificate number: 346/KEPK-FKM/UNIMUS/2020.

Measurement of job satisfaction was using a questionnaire. The research instrument is arranged based on the measured variable indicators: variable context factor and content factor. Context factor indicators include: i) Primary health care policies; ii) Supervisor/supervision; iii) Salary; iv) Interpersonal relationships; and v) Working conditions. Each indicator consists of 5 questions, while the content factor includes: i) Responsibility; ii) Progress in work; iii) Opportunities for achievement; iv) Recognition of performance; and v) Work value [16], [17]. The instrument has been through expert testing for content validity and declared valid at the context validity. Pearson product-moment test revealed that the instrument variable context factor consists of 25 items with a value of $r=0.430-0.777$, and the content factor instrument consists of 26 items with a value of $r=0.429-0.763$. The instrument has been declared reliable with an alpha value of 0.970.

Respondents were given an explanation about the study before data collection. The respondents agreed to join the study by signing an informed consent sheet. Data were collected by direct interviews with respondents by referring to the questions in the questionnaire. Researchers maintain confidentiality by not including the identity of the research subject or anonymous. The research data that has been obtained was carried out by descriptive analysis on each variable and indicator. The characteristics of respondent can be seen in Table 1, meanwhile job satisfaction data is presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 1. Respondents' characteristics

Indicator	F	%
1. Age		
Young adult (≤ 30 years old)	64	44
Adult (> 30 years old)	81	56
2. Gender		
Male	46	31.8
Female	99	68.2
3. Length of work		
Beginner (< 60 months)	11	7.6
Expert (≥ 60 months)	134	92.4
4. Marital status		
Married	103	71
Single	42	29
5. Employment status		
Civil servant	95	65.5
Non civil servant	50	34.5
6. Job position		
Nurse coordinator/head of nurse	11	7.6
Nurse operational	134	92.4

Tabel 2. Distribution frequency of job satisfaction among nurses context factor

Indicator	F	%
1. Satisfaction with Public Health Care's policies		
No	42	29
Yes	103	71
2. Satisfaction with supervision		
No	56	38.6
Yes	89	61.4
3. Satisfaction with salary		
No	39	27
Yes	106	73
4. Satisfaction with interpersonal relationships		
Yes	113	78
No	32	22
5. Satisfaction with working conditions		
No	49	33.8
Yes	96	66.2

Tabel 3. Frequency distribution of job satisfaction among nurses content factor

Indicator	F	%
1. Satisfaction with responsibility		
Yes	80	55.2
No	65	44.8
2. Satisfaction with the progress at work		
No	53	36.6
Yes	92	63.4
3. Satisfaction with the opportunity for achievement		
Yes	79	54.5
No	66	45.5
4. Satisfaction with recognition of performance		
Yes	85	58.6
No	60	41.4
5. Satisfaction with the value of work		
Yes	95	65.5
No	50	34.5

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Respondent characteristics

Indicators of respondent characteristics measured in this study included: i) Age; ii) Gender; iii) length of Work; iv) Marital status; v) Employment status; and vi) Job position. Most of respondent were adult 56%, female 68.2%, length of work ≥ 60 months, married 71%, civil servant 65.5% and as nurse operational 92.4%. The data can be seen in Table 1.

3.2. Nurse job satisfaction

Nurse job satisfaction is identified through context factors can be seen in Table 2 and content factors can be seen in Table 3. Context factor indicators include: i) public health care's policies; ii) implementation of supervision; iii) wages or salaries; iv) interpersonal relationships; and v) working conditions. Indicators of content factor include: i) Responsibility; ii) Progress at work; iii) Opportunities for achievement; iv) Recognition; and v) Work value.

Nurse job satisfaction is an assessment response to the conditions by nurses in the clinical setting. Job satisfaction is subjective which is the impact of the needs that exist in a person associated with the conditions received. Job satisfaction is influenced by motivation, commitment, and work discipline [17].

Factors that affected job satisfaction is a content factor included: responsibility, progress, opportunities for achievement, recognition, and job value. While the context factors include: i) Applicable policies within the company; ii) Supervision; iii) Wages/salaries; v) Interpersonal relationships; and v) Working conditions [18]. Context factors can encourage someone to meet the needs of lower levels. Failure to fulfill context factors can make staff dissatisfied.

Indicators that built job satisfaction (content factor) in this study are: a big responsibility for nurse's work (55.2%). Progress in work developed well (63.4%). Nurses had the opportunity to achieve achievement (54.5%). Nurses also get great recognition for performance (58.6%) and feel their work is valuable (65.5%). Based on the results above, it can be concluded that factors that can encourage people to be able to meet the needs of their upper level have been met. As a result, nurses become satisfied with their work. Meanwhile, indicators that lead to job dissatisfaction (context factor) in this study were: most respondents consider the

primary health care policy to be appropriate (71%) and support supervisors/supervision (61.4%) and consider their salaries to be appropriate (73%). The interpersonal relationship among nurses quite good (78%) and working situations were appropriate (66.2%). Based on the result above, it can be concluded that factors related to the work environment have provided opportunities for nurses to fulfill lower-level needs, therefore prevent nurses to be dissatisfied with their work.

Each individual has different job satisfaction according to the value system adopted. Individual perceptions of a value affect their expectations. Matching between expectations and what is received in the job, may impact job satisfaction [18]. The description of the indicators that cause job dissatisfaction (context factors) in this study are as follows:

3.2.1. Satisfaction with public health center's policies

Public health center's policies that nurses feel so far has been in accordance with the wishes of nurses. It can be seen from several statements of respondents where policymaker at the primary health care always discussed widely and openly to nurses (87%), primary health care always encourages nurses to continue to develop (83%) and each assignment is clearly defined so that nurses can understand their duties, responsibilities, and rights properly (80%). Policies can determine the type of job of nurses, workload, responsibility, promotion system, wages/salary, and work environment either physically or psychologically [18], [19]. Therefore, policies that were based on nurses' needs and fairly (fair and just) will be able to improve job satisfaction [17].

3.2.2. Satisfaction with supervision

Most of the respondents in this study mentioned that supervision had good applied and received good support, this is reflected in the following statements; their leaders had treated nurses with respect as many as 121 people (83.4%) and leaders had provided support and high work motivation, about 116 people (80%), willing to receive nurse suggestions of 112 people (77.2%). The study shows that job satisfaction can be improved with direct supervision because direct supervision related to friendly, understanding, listening, and positive reinforcement. Supervision is an important part of nursing service management which is useful for managing any problems quickly. Good supervisors are able to motivate nursing staff to work in a comfortable atmosphere and enjoyable. So, these also can improve job satisfaction [20].

3.2.3. Satisfaction with salary

Salary is in accordance with the wishes of nurses, it can be seen from several statements which strengthen; nurses receive increases salary periodically and automatically by 95 people (65.5%). Received appropriate salary each month 74 people (51%), but there are some nurses who mention that they received salary inappropriate where the income received was not sufficient to meet the daily needs of 24 people (16.6%). If the salary is given fairly according to job demands, individual skill level, and community wage standard, it will likely result in worker satisfaction [18]. A person will feel satisfied if there is no gap between expectations and reality. The bigger the gap, the bigger dissatisfied. Vice versa, if salary received are higher than expected, it will improve job satisfaction [21].

3.2.4. Satisfaction with interpersonal relationships

This study illustrated that the interpersonal relationship in public health care is quite good. It can be seen by the data from nurse's statements, nursing activities by team and helps each other between colleagues as many as 138 people (95.2%) and they feel well accepted as a team of 131 people (90.3%). A harmonious relationship with superiors will make subordinates respect their superiors and every task given will be done well and with full sincerity. The existence of a relationship that is mutually supportive and caring for each other between colleagues will create a comfortable and warm work environment that results in job satisfaction for nurses [22], [23].

3.2.5. Satisfaction with working conditions

The majority of nurses understand with the working conditions and high responsibility at the public health center were suitable and supported the duties in providing nursing services. It was indicated by several statements that the workflow in the nursing department is well supported about 128 people (88.3%), the division of tasks in the nursing section can assist in providing services to 126 patients (86.9%), and a manual standard operating procedure for the implementation of nursing tasks is already supported for 116 people (80%). Many studies state that employees prefer a physical environment that is not dangerous in terms of place, facilities, and infrastructure. The comfort of the workplace can make nurses feels at home in their workroom to carry out his duties. A work environment that is too extreme, such as air temperature, lighting, ventilation, and noise will affect job satisfaction because it can cause physical disturbances [24]. The description of the indicators that cause job satisfaction (content factor) in this study is as follows:

3.2.6. Satisfaction with responsibility

The majority of nurses understand with the working conditions and high responsibility at the public health center. Understanding working conditions will encourage a person's initiative to feel that the workplace is more friendly [25]. This is in accordance with the statement of the respondent who states that they have been given the freedom to carry out his work as a nurse as many as 100 people (69%) and is often involved by the leadership in making important decisions related to work as many as 73 people (50.3%). Nurses who have high personal responsibility can find out whether a nurse in doing work will be able to improve productivity in accordance with the standards desired by an organization or not [26], [27]. Someone who has high personal responsibility will actively try to show commitment, behavior, and lifestyle that can maximize achievement and fully actualize themselves according to their own ways [24].

3.2.7. Satisfaction with the work progress

This study shows that nurses have been given many opportunities to improve the ability to provide professional nursing services, this is reflected in the statement of respondents that the leadership has given permission to take part in training, courses, seminars, and a higher level of study about 129 people (89%) and leaders encourage to always improve skills in nursing as many as 120 people (83%). A person who is promoted is generally considered to have good achievements, and there are also several other supporting considerations [28], [29]. Promotion levels can increase the enthusiasm and passion of employees at work.

3.2.8. Satisfaction in the opportunity for achievement

In this study, the nurses feel that they have the opportunity to achieve and improve their abilities, this is in accordance with what they said that the leadership conducted an evaluation (feedback) to improve employee performance as many as 106 people (73.1%) and the leadership always encouraged to improve performance by 104 people (71.7%). Good employee performance can increase the award received. Appropriate and fair rewards according to employees will increase job satisfaction. Likewise, if the award is deemed inappropriate, it will also result in decreased job satisfaction [26], [27]. The relationship between job satisfaction and job performance becomes an interacting and sustainable system. An organization must have a career management system for employees. Career development can increase work productivity while reducing the adverse effects of work [30]. Career management is able to improve the creativity of human resources and foster commitment for employees to improve performance to achieve organizational goals.

3.2.9. Satisfaction with recognition of performance

The description of recognition of the performance among nurses in this study mostly stated that they received recognition for their performance, especially related to the performance appraisal system at the primary health care. Recognition in this study mean formal acknowledgement of their existence as health professionals. The recognition was not favoritism for 104 people (71.7%) and the ideas of nurses for changes were well received by the leadership because the performance of nurses was good for 78 people (53.8%). Recognition of employee abilities can improve job satisfaction. This is because the employee's need to feel valued can be fulfilled. This recognition can also improve employee motivation. With good motivation, employees will be able to work optimally [21].

Employees' success influenced by self-confidence and consistent work motivation. As a social human being has a need for self-actualization. Recognition by an organization or company can improve teamwork. Besides, there is also a need for mutual understanding among team members to achieve optimal organizational performance [21]. Basically, everyone likes to be appreciated by others. In fact, most of the workers consider personal recognition to be more motivating than material rewards [17].

3.2.10. Satisfaction of job value

In satisfaction of job value, they understand well their duties and responsibilities as a nurse. They have understood well the job description as a nurse 138 people (95.2%) and the jobs given in accordance with the skills/competencies that they have 129 people (89%). No matter how small the work we did, if we understand that the work is part of a big plan, or that the work is a process towards the realization of something big, then there will be no small feelings in our hearts when doing that work. Job satisfaction itself is the main source of satisfaction, where the job provides interesting tasks, opportunities to learn, opportunities to accept responsibility, and progress for employees [29].

4. CONCLUSION

The study revealed that most of the respondents were satisfied to their job. Aspects that meet the job satisfaction of nurses in this study were: i) Satisfaction with appropriate salaries; ii) Satisfaction with

comfortable working conditions; iii) Satisfaction with responsibility as a nurse by dividing tasks equally among all nurses so that they feel involved in the process of improving care services; iv) Satisfaction with the opportunity for achievement by giving encouragement among nurses to always improve their performance and provide varied or different tasks; and v) Satisfaction with recognition of their performance through giving rewards that are more than criticism and giving appreciation for their performance both financial and non-financial. However, nurses' job satisfaction on the content factor still needs to be optimized. This is supported by the job satisfaction of nurses on the indicators of responsibility, achievement, performance recognition that has not reached 60%.

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